
Recent advance in gene therapy for Leber hereditary optic neuropathy: a systematic review

(Supplemental Materials)

Supplemental Material

Supplemental Material 1. Search strategy

Supplemental Material 2. Assessment of Cochrane Risk of Bias tool (ROB)

Supplemental Material 3. Assessment of Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) tool

Supplemental Material 1
Search strategy

Supplemental Material 1

Search strategy

Primary search steps:

1. Leber hereditary optic neuropathy
2. Leber hereditary optic atrophy
3. Leber optic atrophy
4. LHON
5. gene therapy
6. recombinant gene
7. gene delivery
8. (#1 or #2 or #3 or #4) and (#5 or #6)

Final syntax in PubMed (an example):

(((Leber hereditary optic neuropathy) OR (Leber hereditary optic atrophy)) OR (Leber optic atrophy)) OR (LHON)) AND (((gene therapy) OR (recombinant gene)) OR (gene delivery)) Sort by: Publication Date

Supplemental Material 2
Assessment of
Cochrane Risk of
Bias tool (ROB)

Supplemental Material 3

Assessment of Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) tool

Supplemental Material 3

Assessment of Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) tool

Trials	Selection				Comparability	outcomes			Total quality score
	Representativeness of the exposed cohort	Selection of the non-exposed cohort	Ascertainment of exposure	Demonstration that outcome of interest was not present at start of study	Comparability based on the design or analysis	Assessment of outcome	Was follow-up long enough for outcomes to occur	Adequacy of follow up of cohorts	
NCT02161380	*	*	*		*	*		*	6
NCT03153293	*	*	*		*	*		*	6
NCT03406104	*	*	*		**	*	*	*	7
EUDRACT N° 2013-001405-90.	*	*	*		**	*	*	*	7